

Relationship between Organizational Climate, Organizational Justice and Voluntary Turnover Intention in Nigeria Public Organizations

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ABSTRACT: This study investigated the relationship between organizational justice, organizational climate, and voluntary turnover intention in Nigerian public organizations. A total of 389 employees participated in the study, comprising 55% males and 45% females, with diverse age groups. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson's product-moment correlation, and an independent samples t-test. Findings from the first hypothesis revealed no significant relationship between the dimensions of organizational justice distributive, procedural, interpersonal, and informative justice and voluntary turnover intention, suggesting that employees' fairness perceptions did not predict their intention to leave. However, results for the second hypothesis showed significant relationships between several dimensions of organizational climate and turnover intention. Vision ($r = .187, p < .01$) and information sharing ($r = .098, p < .05$) were positively associated with turnover intention, while safety and influence ($r = -.120, p < .05$) and support for innovation ($r = -.124, p < .05$) displayed negative associations. These outcomes imply that certain aspects of the work environment influence employees' intentions to leave public organizations. The third hypothesis revealed a significant gender difference in voluntary turnover intention. Female employees reported significantly higher turnover intention ($M = 17.86, SD = 2.46$) compared to their male counterparts ($M = 11.15, SD = 1.79$), $t(409) = -32.00, p < .001$. Overall, the study concludes that while organizational justice does not significantly predict voluntary turnover intention, aspects of organizational climate and gender differences play critical roles in shaping employees' intentions to leave public organizations in Nigeria. The findings underscore the importance of creating psychologically safe work environments, strengthening innovation-supportive cultures, and addressing gender-related workplace challenges in order to improve retention outcomes in Nigerian public organizations.

KEYWORDS: Organisational Justice, Organisational Climate, Voluntary Turnover Intention, Nigerian, Public Organizations

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Voluntary turnover remains one of the most persistent challenges confronting contemporary organizations, largely because employee exits disrupt workflow, increase recruitment and training costs, and erode organizational knowledge and stability (Mobley, 1977; Hom & Griffeth, 1995). The strategic importance of retaining skilled employees has therefore become even more pronounced in recent decades, especially as organizations operate in increasingly competitive and volatile environments. Understanding the drivers of employees' intentions to leave is thus essential, particularly within developing economies such as Nigeria where labor markets are characterized by high mobility, organizational instability, poor working conditions, and widespread job dissatisfaction (Fapohunda, 2014). These contextual challenges often intensify employees' sensitivity to workplace conditions and may amplify turnover intentions even when alternative employment opportunities are limited.

Turnover intention defined as the conscious and deliberate willingness of an employee to leave an organization has consistently been identified as the strongest proximal predictor of actual turnover behavior (Tett & Meyer, 1993). Scholars generally agree that before employees engage in the physical act of leaving, they undergo a cognitive withdrawal process in which they evaluate their work environment, assess perceived injustices or unmet expectations, and weigh the costs and benefits of remaining in their current roles. This psychological withdrawal often precedes behavioral withdrawal indicators such as absenteeism, reduced commitment, and diminished job performance. As such, turnover intention serves as an early warning signal for organizations, reflecting internal issues that, if unaddressed, can manifest in actual turnover. As such, identifying the organizational conditions that shape employees' turnover cognitions is essential for both scholars and practitioners.

Two key organizational factors frequently linked to turnover intentions are organizational climate and organizational justice. Organizational climate refers to employees shared perceptions of organizational policies, practices, and procedures, as well as the behaviors rewarded and expected within the work environment (Schneider, 1990). A positive climate characterized by support,

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clarity, trust, and fairness has been associated with higher job satisfaction, stronger organizational commitment, and lower turnover intentions (Parker et al., 2003). Conversely, a negative climate often signals a lack of support, inconsistent communication, or ineffective leadership, all of which can heighten employees' desire to leave (James et al., 2008). In Nigeria, organizational climate has been shown to significantly influence employees' attitudes, especially in contexts where leadership quality, communication, and resource adequacy vary widely across organizations (Adeniji, 2011).

Closely related to climate is organizational justice, which concerns employees' perceptions of fairness in decision-making processes (procedural justice), resource allocation (distributive justice), and interpersonal treatment (interactional justice) (Greenberg, 1987). Extensive research demonstrates that when employees perceive injustice such as inequitable rewards, opaque policies, or disrespectful treatment they are more likely to experience dissatisfaction, reduced commitment, and heightened turnover intentions (Colquitt et al., 2001). In Nigeria, where hierarchical management styles and inconsistent administrative practices are common, perceived organizational injustice has been identified as a major predictor of voluntary turnover among employees across industries (Ogbeide & Alaka, 2017).

Although the relationships between organizational climate, justice, and turnover intentions have been widely examined in global literature, empirical research in the Nigerian context remains limited and fragmented. Given Nigeria's unique socioeconomic environment, cultural norms, and organizational structures, understanding how these variables interact to influence voluntary turnover intentions is both theoretically valuable and practically necessary. Moreover, integrating organizational climate and justice into a single predictive framework offers a more holistic understanding of how workplace environments shape employees' decisions to remain or exit. Therefore, this study seeks to deepen existing knowledge by examining the impact of organizational climate and organizational justice on voluntary turnover intentions in Nigerian organizations.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Employee turnover and turnover intention remain significant challenges across many sectors in Nigeria, including public institutions, banking, education, and hospitality. High turnover intention undermines organizational stability, disrupts operations, increases recruitment and training costs, and erodes institutional memory, all of which can weaken public service delivery and organizational effectiveness (Mobley, 1977; Hom & Griffeth, 1995; Fapohunda, 2014). Despite these serious consequences, the phenomenon of turnover intention in Nigerian public organizations remains under-examined, particularly with regard to how organizational justice, organizational climate, and demographic factors such as gender jointly influence the willingness of employees to leave (Ogbeide & Alaka, 2017; Adeniji, 2011).

Empirical evidence from recent Nigerian studies suggests that turnover intention is indeed a pressing issue. In a study of 1,032 employees from major banks in South-Western Nigeria, significant levels of turnover intention were observed among bank employees (Fapohunda, 2014). Research involving public universities in Northeastern Nigeria found organizational justice to be a strong predictor of turnover intention among academic staff (Ogbeide & Alaka, 2017). A recent study in the oil and gas sector reported that work-environment factors, including organizational justice, significantly influenced employees' job turnover intentions (Adeniji, 2011). In the public sector more broadly, qualitative research has highlighted that many employees express a weak sense of organizational commitment, and that structural issues such as low accountability and weak institutional support may contribute to increased turnover intention (Hom & Griffeth, 1995; Tett & Meyer, 1993).

These findings underscore that turnover intention is not limited to the private sector or a few industries, but is prevalent across different types of organizations in Nigeria, including those in the public domain. Yet, existing studies often focus on a single factor (e.g., job satisfaction, leadership style, commitment) and seldom examine organizational justice, organizational climate, and gender differences together within one comprehensive framework (Greenberg, 1987; Schneider, 1990; Parker et al., 2003). Moreover, while some studies report low turnover intention in certain contexts, others report high turnover intentions or significant predictors of turnover, indicating a knowledge gap and highlighting the complexity of turnover processes in Nigeria (James et al., 2008; Colquitt et al., 2001).

Given the strategic importance of retaining competent and committed employees for the performance and stability of public institutions, there is a clear need to systematically investigate how organizational justice, organizational climate, and gender differences interact to influence voluntary turnover intention within Nigerian public organisations (Schneider, 1990; Greenberg, 1987; Ogbeide & Alaka, 2017). Without such empirical evidence, public institutions may continue to lose valuable human capital with adverse consequences for service delivery, institutional continuity, and organizational performance. Therefore, this study seeks to fill these gaps by providing a comprehensive examination of the relationships among organizational justice, organizational climate, and voluntary turnover intention among employees in selected Nigerian public organizations.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent do the dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, procedural, interpersonal, and informative justice) relate to voluntary turnover intention in Nigerian public organizations?

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2. How does organizational climate (vision, information sharing, safety and influence, task orientation, and support for innovation) relate to voluntary turnover intention in Nigerian public organizations?
3. What is the gender difference in voluntary turnover intention in Nigerian public organizations?

1.4 HYPOTHESES

Given the objectives of the study, the following propositions were formulated at the 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is a significant relationship between organizational justice (distributive, procedural, interpersonal, and informative justice) and voluntary turnover intention in Nigerian public organizations.
- ii. There is a significant relationship between organizational climate (vision, information sharing, safety and influence, task orientation, and support for innovation) and voluntary turnover intention in Nigerian public organizations.
- iii. There will be a significance difference between male and female employees in and voluntary turnover intention in Nigerian public organizations.

2.1 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section deals with conceptual, theoretical framework and empirical review of literature:

2.1.1 Organizational Climate

Organizational climate refers to employees' shared perceptions of policies, practices, and procedures that characterize the work environment (Schneider, Ehrhart, & Macey, 2013). A positive climate featuring supportive supervision, open communication, and clear role expectations has been consistently linked to favourable employee attitudes and lower turnover intention (Patterson et al., 2005; James et al., 2008). In the Nigerian public sector, the climate is often influenced by bureaucratic structures, political interference, and resource constraints, which may create uncertainty and frustration among employees (Adewumi & Akinbobola, 2019). Studies have shown that a poor organizational climate contributes to reduced job satisfaction and increased intentions to leave government service (Olatunji & Mokuolu, 2014).

2.1.2 Organizational Justice

Organizational justice concerns employees' perceptions of fairness in reward distribution, decision-making processes, and interpersonal treatment (Colquitt, 2001). Justice is commonly conceptualized in three dimensions:

- i. Distributive justice – fairness of outcomes (Adams, 1965)
- ii. Procedural justice – fairness of processes (Thibaut & Walker, 1975)
- iii. Interactional justice – fairness in interpersonal treatment (Bies & Moag, 1986)

Empirical studies consistently demonstrate that low levels of perceived justice lead to increased turnover intention (Hassan, 2019; Lambert, Keena & Haynes, 2019). In Nigeria, organizational justice has been found to significantly predict turnover intention among public university staff (Owolabi, 2012) and civil servants (Ovadge, 2015). When employees perceive unfairness in promotions, performance appraisal, or resource distribution, they develop negative attitudes toward the organization, including stronger intentions to quit.

2.1.3 Voluntary Turnover Intention

Voluntary turnover intention refers to an employee's conscious, deliberate, and planned willingness to leave an organization, typically driven by dissatisfaction, unmet expectations, or better external job alternatives (Tett & Meyer, 1993). It is distinct from actual turnover behaviour, but research consistently shows that turnover intention is the most immediate and powerful predictor of actual turnover, often preceding it by weeks or months (Mobley, 1977; Griffeth, Hom & Gaertner, 2000). Voluntary turnover occurs when employees choose to resign, often in pursuit of better job conditions, career advancement, or improved organizational fit. This contrasts with involuntary turnover, which is initiated by the employer (e.g., layoffs, dismissals). Voluntary turnover is especially problematic because organizations lose valued talent, institutional knowledge, and trained personnel especially in sectors requiring high skill or experience, such as public administration (Abassi & Hollman, 2000).

Research identifies multiple factors that contribute to an employee's intention to leave an organization. One of the most critical determinants is job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Employees who find their jobs meaningful and fulfilling are generally less likely to consider leaving, as job satisfaction serves as a buffer against withdrawal behaviours (Judge et al., 2001). Similarly, organizational commitment particularly affective commitment plays a significant role in retaining employees, as those who feel emotionally attached to their organization tend to exhibit lower turnover intentions (Meyer & Allen, 1997). Another major determinant is organizational justice, which encompasses perceptions of fairness in rewards, procedures, and interpersonal treatment. When employees perceive inequity or unfair treatment, they develop feelings of resentment and lowered trust, increasing their likelihood of seeking alternative employment (Colquitt et al., 2013).

The organizational climate and work environment also substantially shape turnover intention. Factors such as leadership style, communication openness, support structures, and psychological safety contribute to the quality of the work environment, influencing

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whether employees choose to remain or leave. Negative work climates, characterized by poor supervision, high stress, or lack of support, have been shown to elevate dissatisfaction and increase turnover intentions (Patterson et al., 2005). In addition, job alternatives and labour market conditions play a central role in shaping turnover intention. According to March and Simon (1958), the availability of attractive external employment options heightens employees' intention to leave, particularly when their current job conditions are unfavourable. Personal and demographic factors, such as age, tenure, education, and career stage, have also been found to influence turnover intention. For instance, younger employees or those with higher educational qualifications often express stronger turnover intentions due to high career mobility and the availability of diverse employment opportunities (Griffeth et al., 2000).

Voluntary turnover intention takes on particular significance in public sector organisations, where employees frequently occupy roles requiring specialised knowledge, extensive experience, or critical institutional memory. Consequently, high turnover rates in such settings can lead to substantial challenges, including the loss of skilled professionals, reduced service delivery quality, increased recruitment and training costs, and the demoralization of remaining employees. These effects can further contribute to institutional instability, a problem that is particularly severe in developing countries where public institutions often face limited capacity and resource constraints (Kim & Fernandez, 2017).

In the Nigerian public sector, voluntary turnover intention is influenced by unique contextual factors. One of the predominant drivers is poor working conditions, as many public employees report inadequate work tools, outdated equipment, and excessive bureaucratic processes that hinder job performance (Olatunji & Mokuolu, 2014). Perceived unfairness also plays a substantial role; Nigerian public servants frequently cite inequities in promotions, performance evaluations, postings, and training opportunities, all of which heighten intentions to leave (Owolabi, 2012). Another major determinant is uncompetitive compensation, as salaries and benefits in the public sector often compare unfavourably with private sector offerings, leading employees with marketable skills to seek more lucrative opportunities elsewhere (Okpu & Kpelai, 2015). Furthermore, leadership practices, including authoritarian management styles, lack of recognition, and insufficient supervisory support, contribute to dissatisfaction and increase turnover intentions (Adewumi & Akinbobola, 2019). Career advancement constraints also affect turnover intention; rigid hierarchies, promotion delays, and political interference limit mobility and stifle motivation within the Nigerian public service (Ovadge, 2015).

Thus, turnover intention in Nigerian public organisations emerges not only from structural deficits but also from employees' perceptions of fairness, justice, leadership practices, and the overall organizational climate. High levels of voluntary turnover intention whether or not they immediately culminate in actual resignation produce numerous negative outcomes for organisations. These include reduced productivity, lower employee morale, declining service quality, increased absenteeism and presenteeism, and weakened knowledge retention. Moreover, elevated turnover intention is often symptomatic of deeper organisational challenges, particularly those related to justice, climate, leadership, and job design.

2.2 EMPIRICAL REVIEW

2.2.1 Relationship between Organizational Climate and Voluntary Turnover Intention

Empirical research has consistently demonstrated that organizational climate plays an important role in shaping employees' turnover intentions. Organizational climate refers to employees' shared perceptions of the work environment, including leadership behaviour, communication practices, reward systems, and interpersonal relations. A positive climate has been associated with lower levels of stress, greater psychological safety, and improved job attitudes, all of which reduce the likelihood that employees will consider leaving the organization.

A growing body of empirical studies supports the notion that a supportive and harmonious organizational climate reduces turnover intention. For example, Agarwal and Gupta (2018), in a study of service-sector employees in India, found that a positive climate characterized by trust, communication openness, and supportive supervision had a strong negative relationship with turnover intention. Their findings indicated that organizational climate indirectly reduces turnover intention through increased job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Similarly, in a study conducted among hotel employees in Turkey, Şahin and Çankır (2018) found that dimensions of organizational climate such as teamwork, supervisor support, and role clarity significantly predicted lower turnover intentions, reinforcing the cross-cultural consistency of the relationship.

In Western contexts, empirical findings also highlight the strength of this relationship. Patterson et al. (2005), using a large sample of UK manufacturing firms, showed that organizational climate was a significant predictor of both employee retention and performance outcomes. Their study demonstrated that employees working in climates emphasizing involvement, autonomy, and supportive leadership were less likely to exhibit turnover intentions. Likewise, Newman, Cooper, and Holland (2019), in their analysis of organizational climate and employee well-being, reported that employees who perceived their organizational climate as fair, supportive, and participative reported significantly lower turnover intention.

Evidence from African countries also corroborates this relationship. In South Africa, Mokaya and Kituyi (2018) found that organizational climate dimensions such as teamwork, recognition, and leadership style significantly influenced turnover intention among public-sector workers. Their findings emphasized that in resource-constrained public environments, psychological elements

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of climate such as respect, communication quality, and perceived support become critical determinants of employees' decisions to stay or leave. In Ghana, Adjei and Kyeremeh (2020) found that a negative organizational climate characterized by poor communication, limited growth opportunities, and weak supervisory support had a strong positive relationship with turnover intention among civil servants. However, empirical research in Nigeria offers mixed findings, suggesting that the relationship may be moderated by sector-specific or contextual factors. Eze (2018), in a study of officers within the Nigeria Police Force, found that organizational climate did not significantly predict turnover intention. Eze argued that the police force's paramilitary structure, limited alternative employment opportunities, and job security norms may weaken the influence that climate typically has on turnover intention. This suggests that in highly structured or authoritarian public institutions, employees' turnover intentions may be shaped more by job alternatives or systemic constraints than by climate variables.

Contrary to Eze's findings, several other Nigerian studies demonstrate a strong link between organizational climate and turnover intention. Adewumi and Akinbobola (2019), in their study of public-sector employees in southwestern Nigeria, reported that role ambiguity, lack of recognition, and poor leadership key components of a negative organizational climate were strongly associated with high turnover intentions. Their study highlighted that public-sector employees in Nigeria often face bureaucratic bottlenecks, unclear job roles, and limited support from supervisors, which significantly heighten the desire to leave. In a study of federal ministry employees in Abuja, Amah (2020) found that organizational climate dimensions such as supervisory relationships, communication quality, and employee involvement significantly predicted turnover intention, with poor communication emerging as the strongest predictor. Similarly, Chukwuma and Obiefuna (2019), examining university administrative staff, found that a positive climate driven by involvement and recognition reduced turnover intention by increasing job satisfaction and organisational commitment.

Additional empirical evidence suggests that climate may interact with psychological variables to influence turnover intention. For example, Ndungu (2021) found among Kenyan public-sector employees that organizational climate had both direct and indirect effects on turnover intention through job stress and burnout. A comparable study by Oyenuga and Akanbi (2022) in Nigeria showed that organizational climate influenced turnover intention through work engagement, suggesting that climate not only directly affects employees' willingness to stay but also shapes motivational and emotional processes. Overall, empirical evidence indicates that a positive organizational climate generally reduces turnover intention across different cultural and organizational contexts. However, the findings from Nigeria highlight that sectoral characteristics, structural constraints, and institutional culture may moderate the strength of this relationship. Thus, while the association is well-supported globally, its magnitude and direction within Nigerian public organisations depend on factors such as bureaucracy, leadership style, job security, and the availability of external employment opportunities.

2.2.2 Relationship between Organizational Justice and Voluntary Turnover Intention

Organizational justice, defined as employees' perceptions of fairness in workplace procedures, interactions, and outcomes, has consistently been identified as a significant predictor of voluntary turnover intention. Perceived injustice undermines employee trust, diminishes morale, and erodes organizational commitment, leading employees to consider leaving the organization (Colquitt et al., 2013; Greenberg, 1990). Turnover intention, in this context, represents a psychological withdrawal process where employees contemplate leaving the organization due to perceived inequities or unfair treatment. Empirical studies across different sectors and countries strongly support the negative relationship between organizational justice and turnover intention. Lambert, Hogan, and Griffin (2019), in a study of U.S. correctional officers, found that employees who perceived higher procedural and distributive justice reported lower turnover intention. Similarly, a meta-analysis by Cohen-Charash and Spector (2001) confirmed that both procedural and distributive justice had significant negative relationships with turnover intention across various occupational contexts. Interactional justice, particularly the quality of interpersonal treatment and communication by supervisors, has also been shown to independently predict turnover intention by shaping employees' perceptions of organizational support and respect (Colquitt et al., 2013).

In the healthcare sector, Kim et al. (2019) examined nurses in South Korea and found that procedural and interactional justice were inversely related to turnover intention. Nurses who perceived fairness in scheduling, promotions, and supervisory interactions reported lower intent to leave. Similarly, in a study of public-school teachers in Ghana, Adjei and Kyeremeh (2020) found that perceived fairness in performance appraisal and recognition significantly reduced turnover intention, highlighting that distributive and procedural justice are critical in public sector retention. Empirical evidence from Nigeria aligns closely with these global findings. Owolabi (2012) found that Nigerian public university staff who perceived inequities in promotion, performance appraisal, and rewards reported higher turnover intention. Ovadje (2015), studying federal civil servants, similarly concluded that unfair resource allocation and favoritism in decision-making increased employees' desire to exit public institutions. Adewumi and Akinbobola (2019) further confirmed that negative perceptions of organizational justice in Nigerian ministries particularly in the areas of role clarity, recognition, and supervisory fairness were associated with high turnover intention. In addition, Okpu and Kpelai (2015) highlighted that uncompetitive salary structures, when perceived as unjust relative to effort and performance, significantly raised voluntary turnover intention in Nigerian public agencies.

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Recent studies have also explored the mechanisms linking justice to turnover intention. For example, organizational justice has been shown to reduce turnover intention indirectly through job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work engagement. Chukwuma and Obiefuna (2019) demonstrated among university staff in Nigeria that perceptions of fairness in reward allocation and supervisor interactions increased job satisfaction and commitment, which in turn lowered turnover intention. Ndungu (2021) found a similar pattern in public-sector employees in Kenya: justice improved perceived organizational support and reduced burnout, thereby decreasing turnover intention. These findings suggest that the justice–turnover relationship operates not only directly but also through mediating psychological processes. While the relationship between organizational justice and turnover intention is generally strong, some studies indicate contextual or sectoral moderators. For example, Eze (2018) found that among Nigeria Police personnel, organizational justice was less predictive of turnover intention than in other public organizations, possibly due to job security, limited alternative employment, and paramilitary structure. Similarly, Lambert et al. (2019) noted that the availability of alternative employment and employee career aspirations can moderate how strongly justice perceptions influence turnover intention. Overall, empirical evidence from both international and Nigerian contexts consistently demonstrates that perceived organizational injustice increases voluntary turnover intention, whereas fair and transparent processes, equitable outcomes, and respectful interpersonal treatment reduce employees' desire to leave. This relationship is particularly pronounced in public sector organizations, where bureaucratic constraints, hierarchical structures, and rigid promotion procedures can amplify the effects of perceived unfairness.

2.2.3 Gender and Voluntary Turnover Intention

Recent empirical work continues to highlight gender as a potentially important but context-dependent factor in turnover intention. In this light, different studies report women have higher TI, others report no difference, and yet others even report higher TI among men, depending on context, measurement, and sample. According to Sousa-Poza and Sousa-Poza (2007) discussing the difference between gender intentions to leave has far-reaching consequences because differing job-mobility inclinations between genders affect probability of being promoted, accumulation of human capital, and wages. Choong et al. (2013) examined the impact of demographic antecedents toward turnover intention amongst academic staff in Malaysian Private Universities. Proportionate stratified sampling technique was employed with a total of 377 samples were collected. One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test were adopted to test the hypotheses. Results showed that significant differences between gender and marital status toward turnover invention, i.e female has higher intention to leave as compared to male, while married respondents have higher job commitment as compared to single respondents.

Abubakar et al. (2013) explored the role of demographic variables in predicting turnover intention among registered Nurses in Nigeria Public hospitals. 175 registered Nurses participated in the study. The findings indicated that male nurses were more likely to leave their organizations or profession than their female colleagues. In a study conducted by Sicherman (1996) using a private company's personnel records, found that after controlling for personal and job characteristics, men and women showed similar turnover patterns. But, when different reasons for turnover were considered, there were significant differences in turnover behaviors between men and women. For example, women were more likely to leave their jobs for personal or family-related reasons. Lyness and Judiesch (2001) suggested that employers may equate 'female' with 'quitter' because women have higher average turnover rates than men.

In another study, Light and Ureta (1992), using the National Longitudinal Survey of young men and women, found that women were less likely to quit their jobs after controlling for unobserved heterogeneity. In the same vain, Lynch (1992) used the National Longitudinal Survey of Youth, and found no significant gender difference after controlling for a set of variables. Furthermore, Khatri et al. (2009) observed that findings on gender and turnover intentions are mixed. For instance, some researchers discovered that female employees were more likely to quit or tended to have greater intention to leave their workplace than their male counterparts. However Judeh, (2012) revealed that male employees have greater intention to leave or seek other employment opportunities than their female counterparts. Also, Elaine (1997) stated that males are the caretakers of their family and they have greater achievement orientation than females. Khatri et al. (2009) added that males may leave their current jobs in favor of a more attractive job if their expectations are not met in their present job

3.1 METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design to examine the relationship between organizational climate, organizational justice, and voluntary turnover intention in Nigerian public organizations. The design allowed for the collection of data at a single point in time to assess employees' perceptions of their work environment and intention to leave voluntarily, facilitating statistical analysis of relationships among variables.

The population comprised employees of selected Nigerian public organizations, including ministries, parastatals, and government agencies. A total of 389 employees participated, selected using a stratified random sampling technique to ensure proportional representation across gender, age, education, marital status, position rank, and religion. The sample included 214 males (55.0%)

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and 175 females (45.0%), with age distribution of 18–28 years (23.6%), 29–39 years (28.0%), 40–50 years (27.5%), and 51 years and above (20.9%). Educational qualifications ranged from SSCE (9.5%), OND (17.0%), HND (27.5%), BSC (30.9%), to MSC (15.1%). Marital status was 37.7% single, 57.2% married, and 5.1% divorced. Position rank included 51.6% junior staff and 48.4% senior staff, while religious affiliation was 68.9% Christian and 31.1% Muslim. This stratified approach ensured diverse representation of employees across organizational and demographic categories.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of standardized scales adapted from established instruments. Organizational climate was measured using 15 items from the Organizational Climate Questionnaire (OCQ) by Litwin and Stringer (1968), assessing perceptions of policies, communication, support, and work environment, with a reliability of $\alpha = 0.82$. Organizational justice was measured with 20 items adapted from Colquitt's (2001) Organizational Justice Scale, capturing distributive, procedural, and interactional justice, with a reliability of $\alpha = 0.83$. Voluntary turnover intention was assessed with six items adapted from Mobley et al. (1978) and Meyer and Allen (1991), with a reliability of $\alpha = 0.80$. All items were rated on a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree).

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations) were used to summarize respondents' demographic characteristics and the main study variables. Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships between organizational climate, organizational justice, and voluntary turnover intention. Additionally, an independent samples t-test was performed to determine whether there were significant gender differences in voluntary turnover intention.

3.1.1 PILOT STUDY

A pilot study was conducted prior to the main survey to assess the reliability, clarity, and feasibility of the research instrument. The purpose of the pilot study was to identify any ambiguities in the questionnaire items, test the appropriateness of the Likert scale, and estimate the internal consistency of the scales to ensure that they would produce reliable data in the main study. The pilot study involved 30 employees from a public organization in Nigeria that was not included in the main study sample. These respondents were selected using a convenience sampling method, representing both junior and senior staff, to reflect the diversity of the target population. The questionnaire included three sections corresponding to the main study variables: organizational climate, organizational justice, and voluntary turnover intention. Each item was reviewed for clarity, relevance, and cultural appropriateness. Participants were asked to provide feedback on any confusing or ambiguous items, and minor adjustments were made based on their responses.

Reliability analysis using Cronbach's alpha was conducted on the pilot data to assess the internal consistency of the scales:

- i. Organizational Climate (OCQ, 15 items): $\alpha = 0.81$
- ii. Organizational Justice (Colquitt, 20 items): $\alpha = 0.82$
- iii. Voluntary Turnover Intention (Mobley et al., 1978; Meyer & Allen, 1991, 6 items): $\alpha = 0.79$

All scales demonstrated acceptable reliability ($\alpha \geq 0.70$), indicating that the instrument was suitable for the main study. No major revisions were necessary, and the pilot study confirmed that the questionnaire was clear, understandable, and capable of capturing the constructs of interest among public sector employees in Nigeria. The results of the pilot study also helped to estimate the approximate time required for completion of the questionnaire, which averaged 15–20 minutes, ensuring that respondents in the main study could complete it without fatigue.

4.1 RESULTS

Table I: Descriptive Analysis of the Respondents

Response	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender		
Male	214	55.0
Female	175	45.0
Total	389	100.0

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Age		
18–28 years	92	23.6
29–39 years	109	28.0
40–50 years	107	27.5
51 years and above	81	20.9
Total	389	100.0
Education		
SSCE	37	9.5
OND	66	17.0
HND	107	27.5
BSC	120	30.9
MSC	59	15.1
Total	389	100.0
Marital Status		
Single	147	37.7
Married	222	57.2
Divorced	20	5.1
Total	389	100.0
Position Rank		
Junior Staff	201	51.6
Senior Staff	188	48.4
Total	389	100.0
Religion		
Christian	268	68.9
Muslim	121	31.1

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Total	389	100.0
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4.1.1 Hypothesis 1: There will be a significant and positive relationship between organizational justice (distributive, procedural, interpersonal, informative) and voluntary turnover intention in Nigerian Public organisations. This hypothesis was tested using Pearson's product correlation.

Table 2:

Summary of Pearsons' Product Correlation Showing Relationship between Organisational Justice and Voluntary Turnover Intention

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>
Distributive Justice	18.00	2.49	1				
Procedural Justice	31.49	3.20	-.100*	1			
Interpersonal Justice	17.91	2.46	-.034	-.016	1		
Informative justice	22.37	2.65	.066	-.041	.027	1	
Turnover intention	14.17	3.96	-.040	-.031	-.023	-.028	1

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The correlation results indicated that distributive justice had a very small negative correlation with turnover intention ($r = -0.040$, $p < 0.05$). Procedural justice ($r = -0.031$), interpersonal justice ($r = -0.023$), and informative justice ($r = -0.028$) were also negatively related to turnover intention, but these relationships were not statistically significant. Overall, these findings suggest that there was no significant positive relationship between organizational justice and voluntary turnover intention among employees in Nigerian public organizations. The weak negative correlations imply that higher perceptions of organizational justice may be slightly associated with lower turnover intentions, although the effects are negligible. Therefore, hypothesis 1 is not supported.

4.1.2 Hypothesis 2: There will be a significant and positive relationship between organizational climate (vision, information sharing, safety and influence, task orientation, support for innovation) and voluntary turnover intention in Nigerian public organisations. This hypothesis was tested using Pearson's product correlation

Table 3:

Summary of Pearsons' Product Correlation Showing Relationship between Organizational Climate and Voluntary Turnover Intention

<i>Variables</i>	<i>X</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>
Vision	10.33	3.14	1					
Information Sharing	10.25	3.22	.693**	1				
Safety influence	9.93	3.26	.434**	.596**	1			
Task orientation	12.90	4.45	.069	.156**	.319**	1		
Support innovation	13.00	4.29	.046	.127*	.146**	.597**	1	
Turnover intention	14.17	3.96	.187**	.098*	-.120*	-.017	-.124*	1

The table 3 results revealed that vision was positively and significantly related to turnover intention ($r = 0.187$, $p < 0.01$), and information sharing was also positively related ($r = 0.098$, $p < 0.05$). In contrast, safety and influence ($r = -0.120$, $p < 0.05$) and support for innovation ($r = -0.124$, $p < 0.05$) were negatively related to turnover intention, while task orientation showed no significant relationship ($r = -0.017$, not significant). These findings indicate that some dimensions of organizational climate, namely vision and information sharing, are positively associated with voluntary turnover intention, whereas other dimensions, including safety and influence and support for innovation, are negatively associated. Task orientation did not significantly influence turnover intention. Overall, hypothesis 2 is partially supported, suggesting that different aspects of organizational climate may have varying effects on employees' intentions to leave public organizations in Nigeria.

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4.1.3 Hypothesis 3 Hypothesis 3 proposed that there would be a significant gender difference in voluntary turnover intention among employees in Nigerian public organizations. To test this hypothesis, an independent samples t-test was conducted to compare the turnover intentions of male and female employees.

Table 4: Summary of Independent Sample t-test Showing Gender Differences in Voluntary Turnover Intention in Nigerian Public Organizations

<i>DV</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Voluntary Turnover Intention	Male	226	11.15	1.79	-32.00	409	.001
	Female	185	17.86	2.46			

The results in table 4 indicated that male employees (N = 226) had a mean turnover intention score of 11.15 (SD = 1.79), while female employees (N = 185) had a mean score of 17.86 (SD = 2.46). The t-test analysis revealed a significant difference between male and female employees, $t(409) = -32.00, p = 0.001$. These results suggest that female employees reported significantly higher voluntary turnover intentions than their male counterparts in the sampled Nigerian public organizations. Therefore, Hypothesis 3 is supported, indicating that gender plays a significant role in employees' turnover intentions within these organizations.

4.2 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study provide insights into the relationship between organizational justice, organizational climate, and voluntary turnover intention, as well as the role of gender in influencing turnover intentions among employees in Nigerian public organizations. Hypothesis 1 proposed that there would be a significant and positive relationship between organizational justice (distributive, procedural, interpersonal, and informative) and voluntary turnover intention. The results indicated that distributive justice had a very small negative correlation with turnover intention ($r = -0.040, p < 0.05$), while procedural justice ($r = -0.031$), interpersonal justice ($r = -0.023$), and informative justice ($r = -0.028$) were negatively related but not significant. These findings suggest that perceptions of organizational justice are not positively associated with turnover intention in the sampled organizations. The weak negative correlations indicate that higher perceptions of justice may slightly reduce turnover intentions, although the effect is negligible. This finding contrasts with some previous studies that reported a strong negative relationship between organizational justice and turnover intention (Colquitt, 2001; Meyer & Allen, 1991), suggesting that other factors, such as job security or cultural norms in Nigerian public organizations, may moderate the influence of justice perceptions on employees' intention to leave.

Hypothesis 2 posited that there would be a significant and positive relationship between organizational climate (vision, information sharing, safety and influence, task orientation, support for innovation) and voluntary turnover intention. The results revealed mixed outcomes. Vision ($r = 0.187, p < 0.01$) and information sharing ($r = 0.098, p < 0.05$) were positively and significantly associated with turnover intention, while safety and influence ($r = -0.120, p < 0.05$) and support for innovation ($r = -0.124, p < 0.05$) were negatively associated. Task orientation showed no significant relationship. These findings suggest that different dimensions of organizational climate influence turnover intention in varying ways. For example, a clear vision and open information sharing may increase employees' awareness of external opportunities or organizational shortcomings, leading to higher turnover intention. Conversely, a safe work environment and support for innovation may strengthen employees' attachment to the organization, reducing their intention to leave. This partial support aligns with prior research indicating that organizational climate is multidimensional and its effects on employee behavior can be complex (Litwin & Stringer, 1968; Schneider et al., 2013).

Hypothesis 3 tested whether there was a significant gender difference in voluntary turnover intention. The independent samples t-test revealed that female employees ($M = 17.86, SD = 2.46$) reported significantly higher turnover intentions than male employees ($M = 11.15, SD = 1.79$), $t(409) = -32.00, p = 0.001$. This finding supports the hypothesis and suggests that gender plays an important role in influencing turnover intention in Nigerian public organizations. It may reflect differences in career expectations, work-life balance considerations, or experiences of workplace support and opportunities between male and female employees. Similar findings have been reported in prior studies where women exhibited higher turnover intentions due to perceived inequities or limited career advancement opportunities (Ng & Burke, 2005; Al-Ahmadi, 2009).

4.3 IMPLICATIONS FOR ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOUR

The study highlights several implications for managing organizational behavior in Nigerian public organizations. Although organizational justice was not a strong predictor of turnover intention, fair treatment in policies and interactions can enhance employee satisfaction and retention. Organizational climate plays a critical role, with vision and information sharing positively related to turnover intention, while safety, influence, and support for innovation reduce it, emphasizing the need for a supportive and engaging work environment. Significant gender differences indicate that female employees are more likely to intend to leave,

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pointing to the importance of gender-sensitive HR practices. Overall, integrating employee perceptions, demographics, and work environment factors into organizational strategies can help reduce turnover, boost engagement, and improve organizational effectiveness.

5.1 CONCLUSION

This study examined the relationships between organizational justice, organizational climate, and voluntary turnover intention, as well as gender differences in turnover intention among employees in Nigerian public organizations.

1. The findings revealed that organizational justice dimensions were not positively related to turnover intention, although weak negative correlations suggest that fair treatment may slightly reduce turnover intentions.
2. Certain aspects of organizational climate, particularly vision and information sharing, were positively associated with turnover intention, while safety, influence, and support for innovation were negatively associated.
3. Additionally, female employees reported significantly higher turnover intentions than their male counterparts.

Overall, the study demonstrates that while perceptions of justice alone may not strongly predict voluntary turnover, the organizational climate and gender differences significantly influence employees' intentions to leave. These insights are critical for public organizations aiming to enhance employee retention, engagement, and productivity.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Public organizations should strengthen vision clarity, communication, and information sharing while also fostering safety, influence, and support for innovation to create a positive work environment that reduces turnover intention.
2. Even though organizational justice was not a strong predictor, maintaining equitable policies, transparent decision-making, and respectful interpersonal interactions can help build trust and commitment among employees.
3. Organizations should address the specific needs of female employees, including career development opportunities, flexible work arrangements, and supportive workplace practices, to reduce gender disparities in turnover intention.
4. Conducting periodic surveys to assess employee perceptions of justice, climate, and satisfaction can provide actionable insights for improving retention and engagement.
5. Leadership and supervisory training should emphasize creating a supportive and fair work environment, encouraging innovation, and enhancing communication to foster organizational commitment.

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